

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Effect of seedling root dip and main field treatment on *Hirschmanniella mucronata* and rice yield

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A microplot field trial at the OUAT Central Research Station in 1985 kharif investigated suitable control measures for the rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella mucronata*. Jaya seedlings of age 28 d were raised in an untreated nursery with an initial average nematode population of 105/200 cm³

soil. The main experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with 7 treatments (subplot size 4 m²), each replicated 5 times: roots dipped for 6 h in normal water (T₁ = control) or in 0.1% aqueous solutions of isofenphos (T₂), diazinon (T₃), BPMC (T₄), monocrotophos (T₅), oncol (T₆), or carbofuran (T₇). The recommended dose of NPK fertilizer was applied. The treated seedlings were transplanted at a spacing of 20 × 15 cm. Carbofuran was broadcast at 1 kg ai/ha at 50 d after transplanting.

The *H. mucronata* population before transplanting ranged from 131 to

136/200 cm³ soil, but at harvest it was maximum in the control and minimal in T₄ (see table), indicating poor population buildup with BPMC. T₇ and T₄ plots had low nematode populations/gram of root, and supported a greater number of flowering tillers and taller plants at harvest than the other treatments. T₇ had maximum grain harvest, followed by T₂ and T₄, which did not differ significantly. Isofenphos, BPMC, and carbofuran gave yield increases of 21-23% over control, indicating their superiority to the other treatments. □

Effect of seedling root dip and main field treatment on *H. mucronata* and rice yield.^a OUAT, Orissa, India, 1985 kharif.

Treatment ^a	Nematodes (no.)			Flowering tillers (no.)	Plant height (cm)	Yield		Increase (%) over control
	Per 200 cm ³ soil		Per g root			g/4 m ²	t/ha	
	Before planting	Ai harvest						
T ₁	132	395	7.8	4.2	82.0	842	2.1	
T ₂	136	212	4.8	5.0	93.0	1032	2.6	23
T ₃	136	206	5.8	5.0	93.4	960	2.4	14
T ₄	131	182	4.6	5.4	95.8	1017	2.5	21
T ₅	132	199	6.0	5.2	94.4	860	2.2	2
T ₆	134	224	5.6	5.2	94.4	986	2.5	17
T ₇	133	199	4.4	5.6	99.4	1037	2.6	23
CD (0.05)	ns	21	0.8	ns	5.0	52		

^a Mean of 5 replications.

Soil and Crop Management

Response to K application of rice in iron-rich valley soils

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We studied the effect of applied K on Fe toxicity and associated nutritional disorders under conditions of shallow water table in wetland rice soil rich in Fe

at Farm Barapani, East Khasi Hills, Meghalaya (25.7 °N, 91.9 °E). The soil was sandy loam, pH 5.05, 1.55% organic C, Bray's P₁ 6 mg/kg, 55 mg exchangeable K/kg, and 1.97% active Fe.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with eight K treatments (muriate of potash) replicated four times. A basal dose of 80 kg N as urea and 40 kg P as single

superphosphate/ ha were applied. Rice variety Ngoba was transplanted in Jun 1985 (monsoon season). Plant samples taken at 35 and 70 d after transplanting (DT) and total K, P, and Fe contents of grain and straw yield samples were estimated using standard procedures.

Where no K was applied, at 50 DT emerging leaves were erect and narrow. Early symptoms of Fe toxicity were yellowing followed by reddish brown